

1 **Exploring the reduction of energy demand of an eco-roof under different irrigation**
2 **strategies**

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13 **ABSTRACT**

14 A passive system widely used to reduce the energy consumption of a building is the green
15 roof. The main objective of this work was to determine the reduction of energy demand
16 of a green roof without plants, eco-roof, for 20 different irrigation strategies, compared
17 to a traditional roof, for the climatic conditions of southern Europe.

18 The results of the eco-roof showed that the evapotranspiration, ET, value increased when
19 outdoor temperature, wind speed, solar radiation and volumetric water content of the
20 substrate rose, and when outdoor relative humidity decreased. The increase in ET had a
21 significant energy influence on the heat flux, \dot{Q} , such that the higher the ET, the lower the
22 \dot{Q} .

23 The annual \dot{Q} results showed that the eco-roof improved the thermal performance of the
24 building compared to the traditional roof, achieving a high reduction of energy demand,
25 ED, up to 78.7%. The strategy that had the highest ratio between the annual ED to the
26 lowest use of water was watering in alternate days for 20 min in the morning, obtaining
27 an ED value of 46.7%. These results indicate that eco-roofs with a proper irrigation
28 strategy could be used as an efficient passive system for the rehabilitation of old buildings.

29

30 **Keywords:** passive system, energy saving, evapotranspiration, irrigation strategies

31

Nomenclature

A	area [m ²]
C	case study
C_e^g	bulk transfer coefficient [-]
C_h^g	bulk transfer coefficient [-]
c_p	specific heat [J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
D	drainage [l m ⁻²]
ED	energy demand [%]
ET	evapotranspiration [l m ⁻²]
F_g	net heat flux to ground surface [W m ⁻²]
I_{ir}^{\downarrow}	total incoming long-wave radiation [W m ⁻²]
I_s^{\downarrow}	total incoming short-wave radiation [W m ⁻²]
l_g	latent heat of vaporization at the ground surface temperature [J kg ⁻¹]
K	hydraulic conductivity [m s ⁻¹]
P	performance of the eco-roof [W h l ⁻¹]
q_a	mixing ratio of the air [-]
q_g	mixing ratio at the ground surface [-]
Q	thermal energy [W h m ⁻²]
\dot{Q}	heat flux [W m ⁻²]
\dot{Q}_S	sensible heat flux [W m ⁻²]
\dot{Q}_L	latent heat flux [W m ⁻²]
R	rainfall [l m ⁻²]
RH	relative humidity [%]
SR	solar radiation [W m ⁻²]
T_a	air temperature near the soil [K]
T_f	foliage temperature [K]
T_g	ground surface temperature [K]
T_o	outdoor temperature [K]
U	transmittance [W m ⁻² K ⁻¹]
VWC	volumetric water content [m ³ m ⁻³]
W	quantity of irrigation water [l m ⁻²]
W_a	wind speed [m s ⁻¹]
WD	wind direction [°]
WS	wind speed [m s ⁻¹]
z	depth [m]

Greek letters

α_g	albedo of ground surface [-]
ε_f	emissivity of the foliage [-]
ε_g	emissivity of the ground surface [-]
λ	thermal conductivity [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
ρ_{ag}	density of air at ground surface temperature [kg m ⁻³]
σ	Stefan-Boltzmann constant [W m ⁻² K ⁻⁴]

σ_f	fractional vegetation coverage [-]
Subscripts	
a	air
eco	eco-roof
exp	experimental
f	foliage
g	ground
num	numerical
o	outdoor
trad	traditional roof
w	week
y	year

32

33 **1 INTRODUCTION**

34 Over the last few years, awareness about global warming and energy-efficient buildings
35 has increased exponentially. The building sector has a large environmental impact and in
36 Europe it represents 50% of the total energy consumption (Dutil, Rouse, & Quesada,
37 2011). Many studies have been carried out in order to reduce the use of fossil fuel and
38 increase the renewable energy consumption, promoting passive systems and efficient
39 envelopes in buildings (Daly, Cooper, & Ma, 2014), in line with the EU Directives
40 (European Parliament, 2010; European Union, 2012).

41 A passive system widely used globally to reduce the energy consumption of a building is
42 the green roof. In Europe, green roofs are very popular in the Nordic countries and
43 Germany, where this technology has been implemented in more than the 10% of all new
44 buildings (Shafique, Kim, & Rafiq, 2018). They are also commonly used in the
45 rehabilitation of old buildings (Cascone, Catania, Gagliano, & Sciuto, 2018). Green roofs
46 are categorized as extensive, intensive and semi-intensive, based on the thickness of the
47 substrate, the type of plants used and the maintenance required (Cascone, 2019;
48 Mahdiyari, Tabatabaee, Abdullah, & Marto, 2018; Naranjo, Mesa, & Maury, 2020).
49 Previous green roofs research showed notable benefits such as the absorption of CO₂, the

50 reduction of noise pollution and the minimization of the heat island effect in cities
51 (Akbari, Cartalis, & Muscio, 2015; Ziogou, Michopoulos, Voulgari, & Zachariadis,
52 2018). Some studies showed that green roofs reduce the heating and cooling demands of
53 the buildings (Ran & Tang, 2018; Zhang, He, & Dewancker, 2020). Plants of a green roof
54 can decrease the solar radiation transmitted to the soil and function as a wind barrier.
55 Consequentially, the heat conducted to the indoor of the building is reduced and the
56 energy losses due to the wind convection are minimized (Besir & Cuce, 2018; Vaz
57 Monteiro et al., 2017). Furthermore, green roofs contribute to a delay in the storm peak
58 runoff to the drainage system and also enrich biodiversity in cities (Kemp, Hadley, &
59 Blanuša, 2019; Li & Yeung, 2014; Vijayaraghavan, Reddy, & Yun, 2019).

60 One of the major energy benefits of the green roofs is the cooling effect on the indoor
61 conditions due to the evapotranspiration, ET (Speak, Rothwell, Lindley, & Smith, 2013).
62 ET is the combination of two separate processes whereby water is lost on the one hand
63 from the soil surface by evaporation and on the other hand from the plants by transpiration
64 (FAO, 2006). Several studies analysed the influence of ET on the energy behaviour of
65 green roofs (Cascone, Coma, Gagliano, & Pérez, 2019; Susca, 2019; Yang, Wang, Cui,
66 Zhu, & Zhao, 2015). While the different variables affecting ET are well known (FAO,
67 2006), the relative importance of each of these variables differs depending on the
68 environmental conditions. An experimental study in subtropical Hong Kong native-
69 woodland intensive green roof found that solar radiation had the strongest correlation
70 with ET (Lee & Jim, 2018). Another experimental study in a tropical extensive green roof
71 showed that ET was largely dependent on solar radiation, relative humidity and wind
72 speed, but found little influence of substrate moisture (Jim & Peng, 2012). A numerical
73 model of a green roof was developed to determine the ET effects on the heat transfer of
74 a building (Djedjig, Bozonnet, & Belarbi, 2015). The model suggested that a green roof

75 installation is able to decrease the heat flux of the building envelope and the ET reduces
76 further the temperature of the roof surface, providing a greater cooling effect. Other
77 authors evaluated numerically the behaviour of green roofs focusing on the correlation
78 between ET and the volumetric water content, VWC, of the growing media (Kaiser,
79 Köhler, Schmidt, & Wolff, 2019; Santamouris, n.d.). These results showed that the
80 irrigation of a green roof increased ET values and mitigated the urban heat island effect,
81 especially during the warmer periods. An experimental study also evaluated the effect of
82 ET on VWC of both a green roof and a bare substrate for four summer days in Melbourne
83 (Coutts, Daly, Beringer, & Tapper, 2013), suggesting that during the summer period the
84 lack of water in the substrates halted the ET and the cooling effect of the roofs was
85 reduced. The irrigation of green roofs helps to reduce the heat transfer between the
86 exterior and the interior of a building, during the warmer months, and increases its thermal
87 insulation capacity (Azeñas et al., 2018). Some researchers demonstrated that in the
88 coming 30 years many areas in the world will be water stressed, so the goal of irrigation
89 installations of green roofs will be to achieve the maximum energy savings with minimum
90 water consumption (Mechelen, Dutoit, & Hermy, 2015). In recent literature some
91 numerical studies proposed an irrigation controlling method based on the predicted ET
92 and daily weather variables, in order to maximize the efficient use of water (Bandara,
93 Balasooriya, Bandara, & Buddhasiri, 2016). Other types of irrigation strategies were
94 analysed in experimental research studies to identify the optimal irrigation frequency (Lin
95 & Lin, 2011). The results indicated that a substrate which is irrigated twice a week is able
96 to reduce the heat amplitude under the roof slab surface up to 91.6%. A numerical model
97 of a green roof was developed to study the irrigation management (Qin, Peng, Tang, &
98 Yu, 2016), showing that irrigation every 3 days to the field capacity and irrigation every
99 7 days to the saturation moisture content are two efficient watering schemes for the

100 climatic condition of Shenzhen, China. A green roof model was simulated in EnergyPlus
101 software to analyse the sensible heat flux reduction potential of several irrigation
102 scenarios under different climatic conditions (Heusinger, Sailor, & Weber, n.d.). For
103 cities with low excess heat and high annual precipitations, such as London and New York
104 , a sensible heat reduction up to 75% was obtained. However, the irrigation strategies of
105 these models were carried out with equal amount of water in all case studies.

106 Research indicated that the type and characteristics of the substrate play an important role
107 in the insulation of buildings (Gomes, Silva, Valadas, & Silva, 2019; Goussous, Siam, &
108 Alzoubi, 2015; Saadatian et al., 2013). A numerical simulation of different soil thickness
109 showed that the ET of the substrate had a significant effect on the thermal performance
110 of the green roof, especially in summer (He, Yu, Ozaki, Dong, & Zheng, 2017). Several
111 energy simulations were performed in EnergyPlus software to investigate the thermal
112 performance of five types of green roofs substrates (Gagliano, Poli, & Sciuto, 2019). It
113 was found that the thermal performance of green roofs strongly depended on the
114 thermophysical properties of the substrate used. An experimental annual study analysed
115 three different substrates under the Mediterranean climate (Porcaro et al., 2019), showing
116 that a substrate composed of commercial growing medium achieved higher heat flux
117 reduction than substrates composed of recycled construction materials. An experimental
118 study was carried out to evaluate the impact of the substrate and irrigation on the thermal
119 performance of green roofs (Tan et al., 2017). This study suggested that the substrate and
120 the soil moisture reduced the roof temperature and improved the thermal performance of
121 the building. An experimental research study analysed the temperature below the concrete
122 of an eco-roof and of a traditional gravel ballasted roof for a summer week in the south
123 of Italy (Bevilacqua, Mazzeo, Bruno, & Arcuri, 2016). The substrate was not provided
124 with irrigation system. The results showed that this temperature was reduced compared

125 to the traditional roof. In this study, an eco-roof was defined as a green roof without
126 plants.

127 The results obtained in recent literature have shown that irrigation strategies could
128 improve the thermal performance of a building with a green roof. However, most of these
129 studies have focused on a limited number of irrigation strategies with the same amount
130 of water in all cases. Therefore, a detailed analysis of the reduction of energy demand of
131 a building with an eco-roof for different irrigation strategies under Mediterranean climatic
132 conditions could be carried out.

133 The main objective of this work was to determine the reduction of energy demand of a
134 building with an eco-roof under different irrigation strategies compared to a traditional
135 roof. To achieve this, a model of an eco-roof and another of a traditional gravel ballasted
136 roof were calibrated with experimental data and annual energy simulations were carried
137 out to evaluate 20 different irrigation strategies.

138 **2 METHODOLOGY**

139 **2.1 Experimental setup and monitoring system**

140 The energy performance of an eco-roof and a traditional gravel ballasted roof were
141 analysed for the climatic conditions of Córdoba, 37°53'29.6" N 4°46'21.9" O. This city is
142 located in the south of Spain and its climate is Mediterranean, subtype Csa dry-summer,
143 as defined in the Koppen-Geiger climate classification (Kottek, Grieser, Beck, Rudolf, &
144 Rubel, 2006).

145 An experimental setup composed of an eco-roof and a traditional gravel ballasted roof
146 were installed on the rooftop of an old office building from the 1950s, located in the
147 University of Córdoba. The dimensions of the rooftop were 27.7 m length and 9.5 m
148 width and no shadows of trees or other buildings fell on it. The building didn't have a
149 climate control program, so the indoor air conditions were maintained in free evolution.

150 A representation of the eco-roof and the gravel ballasted roof is shown in Fig. 1. The
 151 layers of the eco-roof, from bottom to top, were: roof slab ($\lambda= 2.3 \text{ W/mK}$; $c_p= 1000$
 152 J/kgK), waterproof membrane, root-barrier, water storage layer ($\lambda= 0.17 \text{ W/mK}$; $c_p= 900$
 153 J/kgK), filter sheet and commercial growing medium ($\lambda= 0.52 \text{ W/mK}$; $c_p= 1840 \text{ J/kgK}$)
 154 with a maximum granulometry of 8 mm, see Fig. 1a. The properties of the substrate are
 155 shown in Table 1. The layers of the gravel ballasted roof, from bottom to top, were roof
 156 slab, waterproof membrane and a layer of gravel ballasted ($\lambda= 0.55 \text{ W/mK}$; $c_p= 1000$
 157 J/kgK), see Fig. 1b.

158 Table 1. Properties of the commercial growing medium substrate.

	Value
Saturated-surface-dry density	1.5 [g/cm^3]
Dry density	1.1 [g/cm^3]
Dry bulk density	0.3 [g/cm^3]
Water absorption	41.3 [%]
pH	7.3-7.7
Electric conductivity	2.0 [mS/cm]

159
 160 Ten temperature, T, probes along the vertical profile, two volumetric water content,
 161 VWC, probes and two heat flux, \dot{Q} , probes were installed in the eco-roof, as shown in Fig.
 162 1a. Three temperature, T, probes along the vertical profile and two heat flux, \dot{Q} , probes
 163 were installed in the gravel ballasted roof, as shown in Fig. 1b.

164 All the data were recorded every 15 min, from 1/01/2015 to 31/12/2015, by a dedicated
 165 acquisition system. The technical specification of all the devices used to record the data
 166 are summarized in Table 2.

167

168

Fig. 1. Layers of (a) the eco-roof and (b) the gravel ballasted roof

169

Table 2. Equipment and variables measured in the experimental campaign.

Equipment	Accuracy	Variable	Unit
Thermistors	$\pm 0,25^{\circ}\text{C}$ (-10 to 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Temperature	[$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
Heat flux plate	$\pm 5\%$	Heat flux	[$\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$]
Water content reflectometer	$\pm 2.5\%$ (0 to 50%)	Volumetric water content	[%]
Platinum resistance temperature	0.2°C (-40 to 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Air temperature	[$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
Capacitive relative humidity	2% (0 to 100%)	Air relative humidity	[%]
Silicon photocell solar radiation	5% (350 nm to 1100 nm)	Solar radiation	[W/m^2]
Wind speed and direction sensor	1% (0 to 100 m/s) 3° (0 to 360°)	Wind speed and direction	[m/s] [°]
Rain gauge	98% at 20 mm/h	Rainfall	[m^3/m^3]

170

171 The experimental setup shown in Fig. 1 was used to calibrate two models of a building
 172 with a gravel ballasted roof and an eco-roof. In order to calibrate these models, a climatic
 173 file with the weather conditions of Córdoba was used. The climatic data were measured
 174 throughout 2015 by a weather station situated near the experimental set up. The probes
 175 used by the weather station are shown in Table 2. The data collected were: atmospheric
 176 pressure, outdoor air temperature, T_o , outdoor relative humidity, RH_o , rainfall, R, solar
 177 radiation, SR, wind speed, WS, and wind direction, WD. The monthly average
 178 meteorological data of 2015 are shown in Table 3.

179 Table 3. Monthly meteorological data

Month	T_o [C]	RH_o [%]	SR [Wh/m ²]	WD [°]	WS [m/s]	R [mm]
January	10.6	89.9	90	171.5	1.6	0.041
February	10.9	81.9	116.5	184.4	2.2	0.035
March	11.4	71.9	200.6	201.6	1.5	0.021
April	15.8	66.4	227.1	199.1	1.7	0.072
May	18.6	61.3	257.5	192.6	1.9	0.054
June	24.9	43.5	323.7	206.7	2	0
July	29.1	40.5	318.3	206.9	1.9	0.001
August	27.6	45	265.6	207.8	2	0.002
September	22.5	53.5	221.7	201.2	1.8	0.008
October	18.5	73.8	146.2	155.9	1.3	0.057
November	12.8	77.5	137.1	135.8	1.1	0.043
December	10.2	77.6	95.9	110	1	0.008

180

181 2.2 Building models

182 Two building models were designed in order to simulate the energy behaviour of two
 183 roofs: a traditional gravel ballasted roof and an eco-roof. These models were developed
 184 using DesignBuilder software (“DesignBuilder,” 2014), which is the graphical interface
 185 of EnergyPlus (“EnergyPlus,” 2014). The geometrical and thermal characteristics of the
 186 building were the same for both models, except for the roof. The characteristics of the
 187 building are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Geometrical and thermal characteristics of the office building.

Geometrical characteristics	Height	9.0 [m]
	Number of floors	3
	Floor area	264.0 [m ²]
Thermal characteristics	U external walls	3.0 [W/m ² K]
	U ground	2.0 [W/m ² K]
	U traditional roof	2.9 [W/m ² K]
	U eco-roof	1.3 [W/m ² K]
	U windows	5.7 [W/m ² K]

189

190 The eco-roof energy analysis of the DesignBuilder software was based on the Army Corps
 191 of Engineers' FASST vegetation models (Frankenstein & Koenig, 2004a, 2004b). In this
 192 model the energy budget was divided into a budget for the foliage layer, F_f , and a budget
 193 for the ground surface, F_g , (Sailor, 2008). The overall energy balance at the soil surface
 194 was given by Eq. (1), where the final term is the conduction of heat into the soil. The
 195 present work focused on an eco-roof only with substrate, so the energy balance of the roof
 196 was calculated without the contributions of the plants.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_g = (1 - \sigma_f) \left[I_s^\downarrow (1 - \alpha_g) + \varepsilon_g I_{ir}^\downarrow - \varepsilon_g \sigma T_g^4 \right] - \frac{\sigma_f \varepsilon_g \varepsilon_f \sigma}{\varepsilon_g + \varepsilon_f - \varepsilon_g \varepsilon_f} (T_g^4 - T_f^4) \\
 + \dot{Q}_s + \dot{Q}_L + K \times \frac{\partial T_g}{\partial z}
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

197 Where σ_f is the fractional vegetation coverage (zero in the eco-roof); I_s^\downarrow is the total
 198 incoming short-wave radiation; α_g is the albedo of ground surface; I_{ir}^\downarrow is the total
 199 incoming long-wave radiation; ε_g is the emissivity of the ground surface; T_g is the ground
 200 surface temperature; ε_f is the emissivity of the foliage; σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann
 201 constant; T_f is the foliage temperature; \dot{Q}_s is the sensible heat flux; \dot{Q}_L is the latent heat
 202 flux; K is the hydraulic conductivity and z is the depth.

203 Sensible heat flux, \dot{Q}_s , in an eco-roof depended on the temperature difference between
 204 the soil and the external air and the wind speed, as expressed by Eq. (2).

$$\dot{Q}_s = \rho_{ag} C_{p,a} C_h^g W_a (T_a - T_g) \quad (2)$$

205 Where ρ_{ag} is the density of air at ground surface temperature; $C_{p,a}$ is the specific heat of
 206 air at constant pressure; C_h^g is the bulk transfer coefficient; W_a is the wind speed; T_a is the
 207 air temperature near the soil and T_g is the ground surface temperature.

208 Latent heat flux, \dot{Q}_L , in an eco-roof depended on the difference between the mixing ratio
 209 of the soil surface and air and the wind speed, as expressed by Eq. (3).

$$\dot{Q}_L = C_e^g \cdot l_g \cdot W_a \cdot \rho_{ag} \cdot (q_a - q_g) \quad (3)$$

210 Where C_e^g is the bulk transfer coefficient; l_g is the latent heat of vaporization at the ground
 211 surface; q_a is the mixing ratio of the air near to the soil and q_g is the mixing ratio at the
 212 ground surface.

213 **2.3 Irrigation strategies**

214 Heat flux, \dot{Q} , of an eco-roof under different irrigation strategies was evaluated and
 215 compared to a traditional gravel ballasted roof. The irrigation strategies consisted of
 216 watering at five specific moments of the day with four different quantities of water. The
 217 daily irrigation schedules were: (i) once a day in the morning, (ii) once a day during the
 218 night, (iii) twice a day with the irrigation quantity divided between morning and evening,
 219 (iv) once a day in the afternoon and finally (v) once a day in the morning for alternate
 220 days, i.e. it was irrigated on Monday, Wednesday, Friday and Sunday. The quantities of
 221 irrigation water were: (i) 3.7 l/m²·day, (ii) 7.3 l/m²·day, (iii) 11.0 l/m²·day, (iv) 14.6
 222 l/m²·day, considering that 10 minutes of irrigation corresponded to 1.83 l/m². The
 223 combination of the five schedules and four irrigation quantities resulted in 20 irrigation
 224 strategies, C1₂₀ to C5₈₀, as summarized in Table 5. The numbers 1-5 indicated the daily
 225 irrigation schedule and the subscripts 20-80 indicated the daily minutes of irrigation.

226 The irrigation strategies of the eco-roof were based on a mass balance expressed by Eq.
227 (4).

$$\Delta VWC = W + R - ET - D \quad (4)$$

228 Where ΔVWC is the variation of the volumetric water content stored in the substrate, W
229 is the quantity of irrigation water, R is rainfall quantity, ET is the evapotranspiration and
230 D is the drainage.

231 The irrigation aimed to reduce the heat flux through the roof assembly from the exterior
232 to the interior during the summer period for the considered climatic conditions. For this
233 reason, the irrigation strategies were proposed from May to October, when the exterior
234 air temperature exceeded 18 °C, see Table 3. A case without irrigation strategy, C0, was
235 also studied for the eco-roof, see Table 5.

236

Table 5. Irrigation strategies.

Case studies	Irrigation period [min/day]	Quantity of water [l/m ² day]	Irrigation schedule	Schedule
C0	0	0	-	-
C1 ₂₀	20	3.7	8:30 am	Every day
C2 ₂₀	20	3.7	8:30 pm	Every day
C3 ₂₀	20	3.7	8:30 am/8:30 pm	Every day
C4 ₂₀	20	3.7	1:00 pm	Every day
C5 ₂₀	20	3.7	8:30 am	Alternate days
C1 ₄₀	40	7.3	8:30 am	Every day
C2 ₄₀	40	7.3	8:30 pm	Every day
C3 ₄₀	40	7.3	8:30 am/8:30 pm	Every day
C4 ₄₀	40	7.3	1:00 pm	Every day
C5 ₄₀	40	7.3	8:30 am	Alternate days
C1 ₆₀	60	11.0	8:30 am	Every day
C2 ₆₀	60	11.0	8:30 pm	Every day
C3 ₆₀	60	11.0	8:30 am/8:30 pm	Every day
C4 ₆₀	60	11.0	1:00 pm	Every day
C5 ₆₀	60	11.0	8:30 am	Alternate days
C1 ₈₀	80	14.6	8:30 am	Every day
C2 ₈₀	80	14.6	8:30 pm	Every day
C3 ₈₀	80	14.6	8:30 am/8:30 pm	Every day
C4 ₈₀	80	14.6	1:00 pm	Every day
C5 ₈₀	80	14.6	8:30 am	Alternate days

238

239 2.4 Energy simulation

240 Detailed energy simulations were carried out with the DesignBuilder software
 241 (“DesignBuilder,” 2014). The simulations were performed for the climatic conditions of
 242 Córdoba throughout the whole year 2015.

243 The eco-roof under the different irrigation strategies was studied according to the
 244 following parameters:

- 245 • Evapotranspiration, ET, of the substrate that was calculated directly from the
 246 latent heat flux calculations for the substrate, see Eq. (3), and the corresponding
 247 values of latent heat of water vaporization (Sailor, 2008). Although the term ET
 248 is used throughout the paper, it should be noted that in this study the transpiration
 249 term was zero, as the eco-roof was studied without vegetation. Therefore, all

250 transformation of liquid water from the eco-roof to the atmosphere was through
251 evaporation from the bare soil surface only.

252 • Heat flux, \dot{Q} , obtained in the eco-roof and the traditional gravel ballasted roof.
253 Heat flux of the eco-roof, \dot{Q}_{eco} , was calculated with the sum of sensible heat flux
254 and latent heat flux, expressed by Eqs. (2) and (3), respectively. The heat flux of
255 the traditional gravel ballasted roof, \dot{Q}_{trad} , was calculated with the transfer model
256 based on the conduction transfer functions, CTFs, (Myers, 1980; Seem, 1987). In
257 addition, \dot{Q} was used as calibration parameter of the roof models. The probes used
258 to measure \dot{Q} are shown in Fig. 1. The positive and negative \dot{Q} values indicated
259 heat entering and leaving, respectively. In the present work, the positive \dot{Q} values
260 were evaluated in detail, because the main objective of the eco-roof was to reduce
261 heat flux entering in the building during the warmer seasons, that correspond to
262 the maximum peaks of solar radiation and outdoor air temperature during the day-
263 time, see Table 3.

264 • Energy demand, ED, of the building with the eco-roof under different irrigation
265 strategies, compared to the traditional gravel ballasted roof. ED was calculated by
266 Eq. (5), where Q_{trad} is the sum of the positive gains of the traditional roof and
267 Q_{eco} is the sum of the positive gains of the eco-roof.

$$ED = \frac{Q_{trad} - Q_{eco}}{Q_{trad}} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

268 • The energy performance of the eco-roof, P_{eco} , was analysed with a ratio, in order
269 to evaluate the irrigation strategies that led the highest reduction of energy demand
270 with respect to the lowest amount of irrigation water, expressed by Eq. (6):

$$P_{eco} = \frac{Q_{trad} - Q_{eco}}{W} \quad (6)$$

271 **3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS**

272 **3.1 Calibration of the models**

273 A calibration of the two building models, one with a traditional gravel ballasted roof and
274 one with an eco-roof, was carried out using the heat flux data collected during the
275 experimental campaign, see Fig. 1. The models were calibrated for two typical months
276 under the climatic condition of Córdoba: August, that presented high values of outdoor
277 air temperature and solar radiation, and December, that presented low values of outdoor
278 air temperature and solar radiation, see Table 3. The irrigation schedule in August was
279 1.83 l/m² twice a day, corresponding to the irrigation strategy C3₂₀, while in December
280 no irrigation schedule was considered, C0, see Table 5.

281 The experimental \dot{Q} values with respect to numerical \dot{Q} values of both roofs for the
282 selected months are shown in Fig. 2. It can be observed that R^2 values equal or higher
283 than 0.94 were obtained for both models. Previous studies regarding eco-roof models
284 which were validated experimentally, usually did not provide information on the
285 correlation coefficient R^2 .

286 Fig. 2. Calibration of models of the traditional gravel ballasted roof in (a) August and
 287 (b) December, and the eco-roof in (c) August and (d) December.

288 3.2 Weekly evapotranspiration analysis

289 A weekly analysis of the effects of climatic conditions and the VWC of the substrate on
 290 the ET of the eco-roof was carried out. Two typical weeks for the climatic conditions of
 291 Córdoba were selected for this study: a summer week from 15/08/2015 to 21/08/2015,
 292 where the eco-roof was provided with the irrigation strategy C3₂₀ and a winter week from
 293 02/01/2015 to 08/01/2015 with no irrigation schedule, C0, see Table 5.

294 3.2.1 Effect of climatic variables on evapotranspiration

295 The effects of the climatic variables on the ET were analysed for the two selected weeks.
 296 The climatic variables used were outdoor air temperature, T_o , solar radiation, SR, wind
 297 speed, WS, and outdoor relative humidity, RH_o . The results of this analysis are shown in
 298 Fig. 3. It can be observed that the trends obtained of the climatic variables on ET were
 299 similar for both weeks, although different slopes were obtained. The ET values increased
 300 when the values of T_o , WS and SR rose, see Fig. 3a, Fig. 3c and Fig. 3d, respectively.
 301 However, the ET values increased when the RH_o values decreased, see Fig. 3b. In
 302 previous studies of the effects of climatic conditions on ET, similar trends were obtained
 303 (Cascone et al., 2019; FAO, 2006).

304 For the summer week, the ET values were usually higher than those during the winter
 305 week, see Fig. 3, mainly due to the high values of T_o and SR and low values of RH_o
 306 achieved with respect to those during the winter week. For the winter week, almost all
 307 the ET values were lower than 0.05 mm/h.

308 Fig. 3. Effect of climatic conditions (a) T_o ; (b) RH_o ; (c) SR; (d) WS, on ET.

309 3.2.2 Effect of volumetric water content of the substrate on evapotranspiration

310 An analysis of the effects of VWC on ET for all the irrigation strategies was carried out
 311 for the two weeks studied. The average weekly results of VWC with respect to ET are
 312 represented in Fig. 4. For the summer week, it can be observed that ET values increased

313 when the weekly average of VWC increased. The highest average ET values were
 314 obtained for the irrigation strategies C1₆₀ and C1₈₀, 0.379 mm/h and 0.390 mm/h, with an
 315 average VWC value of 36.6% for both cases, see Fig. 4. The lowest average ET values
 316 were obtained for the irrigation strategies C0 and C3₂₀, 0.008 mm/h and 0.04 mm/h, with
 317 average VWC values of 4.0% and 10.0%, respectively. Thus, it can be said that the
 318 weekly average VWC value of the substrate had a significant impact on ET during the
 319 summer week.

320 For the winter week, the highest average ET values were achieved for the irrigation
 321 strategies C1₄₀ to C5₈₀, see Fig. 4. The case C0, which had no irrigation schedule,
 322 achieved the lowest value of ET, 0.008 mm/h, with an average VWC value of 15.7%. The
 323 average VWC value for C0 depended on the rain during this winter week. The results
 324 obtained for the winter week showed that average ET values did not have a significant
 325 variation when average VWC and irrigation strategy were modified.

326

327

Fig. 4. Average weekly results of ET and VWC of the substrate.

3.3 Weekly energy analysis

A weekly study of the average heat fluxes, \dot{Q} , average evapotranspiration, ET, and irrigation strategies of the eco-roof was performed for the typical summer week selected, from 15/08/2015 to 21/08/2015. However, this analysis was not carried out for the winter week selected, because the ET values did not vary significantly with respect to the different irrigation strategies, as shown in section 3.2.2.

3.3.1 Effect of evapotranspiration on heat flux

The results of the relationship between average heat fluxes, \dot{Q} , and average evapotranspiration, ET, under the irrigation strategies are shown in Fig. 5. The \dot{Q} values represented were the average positive heat flux values, energy flux gains. It can be observed that the average \dot{Q} values were reduced when average ET values increased. This trend was opposite to the relationship between VWC on ET, as shown in Fig. 4. The lowest average \dot{Q} values were achieved for C1₆₀ and C1₈₀, 6.5 W/m² and 6.4 W/m², coinciding with the highest ET values, 0.379 mm/h and 0.39 mm/h, respectively, see Fig. 5. The highest average \dot{Q} values for the cases with an irrigation strategy, were achieved by C3₂₀ and C4₂₀, 29.7 W/m² and 29.3 W/m², respectively. For C0, an average \dot{Q} value of 31.4 W/m² and an ET value close to zero were obtained, due to the absence of irrigation. The results showed that if a significant reduction of \dot{Q} is required, high ET values are needed, i.e. irrigation strategies with a high quantity and frequency of water application should be used.

For the selected summer week, the \dot{Q} value of the traditional gravel ballasted roof was 52.3 W/m², 40% more than the \dot{Q} value of the eco-roof rate with no irrigation strategy, C0. The use of an irrigation strategy for the eco-roof allowed a significant reduction of the average \dot{Q} value, up to 87.7% for the strategy C1₈₀ with respect to the traditional gravel

352 ballasted roof. Therefore, an eco-roof provided with an optimized irrigation strategy
 353 could be used to to reduce the heat transfer through the roof assembly of a building.

354

355 Fig. 5. Average weekly results of ET and \dot{Q} for a typical summer week.

356 3.3.2 Effect of irrigation on weekly energy

357 The relationship between irrigation and \dot{Q} for the different case studies is shown in Fig.
 358 6. Comparing the irrigation strategies with the same quantity of water and different
 359 watering schedule, the results showed that for the case studies C1₂₀ to C5₂₀, the \dot{Q} values
 360 obtained, from lowest to highest, were: C1₂₀, 1829.1 W·h/m²; C2₂₀, 2151.9 W·h/m²; C5₂₀,
 361 2153.9 W·h/m²; C4₂₀, 2195.9 W·h/m², and C3₂₀, 2230.5 W·h/m², see Fig. 6. Therefore,
 362 for these case studies, the irrigation during the morning allowed the greatest reduction of
 363 \dot{Q} to be obtained, as the highest values of ET and VWC were achieved during the
 364 morning, see Fig. 5 and Fig. 4. However, the lowest reduction of \dot{Q} was obtained watering
 365 twice a day with the irrigation quantity divided between morning and evening, C3₂₀.

366 For the irrigation strategies C1₄₀ to C5₄₀, the Q values from lowest to highest were: C1₄₀,
367 1043.8 W·h/m²; C3₄₀, 1440.0 W·h/m²; C5₄₀, 1711.3 W·h/m²; C2₄₀, 1828.2 W·h/m², and
368 C4₄₀, 1838.1 W·h/m², see Fig. 6. Hence, the lowest value of Q was obtained by irrigating
369 during the morning, while the highest was by irrigating at 1pm. These results agreed with
370 the previous ET analysis, see Fig. 5.

371 Among the cases C1₆₀ to C5₆₀, the irrigation strategies with Q values from lowest to
372 highest were: C1₆₀, 189.1 W·h/m²; C3₆₀, 504.1 W·h/m²; C5₆₀, 882.0 W·h/m²; C4₆₀,
373 1198.0 W·h/m²; C2₆₀, 1235.1 W·h/m², see Fig. 6. Therefore, the highest and lowest values
374 of \dot{Q} were achieved by watering during the morning, at 8:30 am, and during the night, at
375 1:00 pm, respectively.

376 Finally, for the cases C1₈₀ to C5₈₀, the irrigation strategies with Q values from lowest to
377 highest were: C1₈₀, 168.5 W·h/m²; C3₈₀, 454.7 W·h/m²; C2₈₀, 695.1 W·h/m²; C5₈₀, 750.9
378 W·h/m²; C4₈₀, 878.8 W·h/m², see Fig. 6.

379 Comparing the irrigation strategies with the same watering schedule and different
380 quantities of water, the results showed that Q value reduced as the quantity of water
381 increased. For the cases C1, with irrigation at 8:30 am, C1₄₀ achieved a Q value 42.9%
382 lower than C1₂₀, while C1₆₀ achieved a Q value 81.8% lower than C1₄₀. However, C1₈₀
383 presented a slight reduction in Q compared to C1₆₀, 10.8%. Therefore, the cases C1
384 followed an asymptotic trend.

385 Regarding cases C2, with irrigation at 8:30 pm. C2₄₀ achieved a Q value 15.0% lower
386 than C2₂₀, while C2₆₀ achieved a Q value 32.4% lower than C2₄₀. Finally, C2₈₀ reduced
387 the \dot{Q} value 56.2% with respect to C2₆₀. It can be observed that the Q results for the cases
388 C2 presented a decreasing linear trend.

389 For the cases C3, strategies with irrigation twice a day, C3₄₀ obtained a Q value 32.4%
390 lower than C3₂₀, C3₆₀ obtained a Q value 65.0% lower than C3₄₀ and, C3₈₀ achieve a

391 slight reduction in Q compared to C3₆₀, 9.8%. Therefore, the cases C3 also followed an
 392 asymptotic trend, as in cases C1.

393 For the cases C4, with the irrigation schedule at 1:00 pm, the Q value of C4₄₀ was 16.3%
 394 lower than C4₂₀, the Q value of C4₆₀ was 34.8% lower than C4₄₀, and finally, the Q value
 395 of C4₈₀ was 26.7% lower than C4₆₀.

396 Regarding cases C5, the strategies with irrigation on alternate days, it can be observed
 397 that C5₄₀ achieved 20.5% of Q values lower than C5₂₀, C5₆₀ achieved 48.4% of Q values
 398 lower than C5₄₀ and, finally, C5₈₀ obtained 14.8% of Q values lower than C5₆₀. Therefore,
 399 the results of the cases C5 presented a decreasing linear trend, with low reduction of Q
 400 values when the watering increased.

401 These results showed that the greatest reduction in Q was obtained for the strategies with
 402 irrigation once a day in the morning, at 8:30 am. In addition, the greater the irrigation of
 403 water, the greater the reduction of Q. In any case, it is important to stress that even with
 404 the same overall quantity of water, important differences in Q can be obtained, simply by
 405 changing the irrigation management. This implies that even under the same water use, it
 406 is important to optimize irrigation scheduling.

407

408

Fig. 6. Relationship between Q and irrigation for a typical summer week.

409 The reduction of Q due to the irrigation strategies, led to weekly reduction of energy
 410 demand, ED_w , in the studied building. The ED_w results of the eco-roof compared to the
 411 gravel ballasted roof for the selected summer week, are shown in Fig. 7. ED_w was
 412 calculated by Eq. (5). The results showed that the ED_w values were always higher than
 413 40% for all the case studies, even for C0 that had no irrigation schedule. Therefore, the
 414 eco-roof had a higher thermal insulation than the considered traditional gravel ballasted
 415 roof.

416 Comparing the irrigation strategies with the same watering schedule and different amount
 417 of water, it can be observed that watering in the morning, cases C1, always allowed higher
 418 ED_w values than those obtained at other schedules to be achieved. The highest ED_w value
 419 was achieved with C1₈₀, 87.8%. Nevertheless, there was no substantial improvement of
 420 the ED_w value between 60 min and 80 min of irrigation, a difference of 0.3%. Therefore,
 421 these results suggest that the irrigation strategy C1 allows the maximum ED_w values to
 422 be obtained for the week of August studied.

423

424

425

Fig. 7. Weekly results of the reduction of energy demand.

426 **3.4 Annual energy analysis**

427 An annual analysis of the reduction of energy demand, ED_y , and performance, P_{eco} , of the
428 eco-roof for all the irrigation strategies was carried out. This analysis was performed from
429 01/01/2015 to 31/12/2015. The irrigation strategies were planned from 01/05/2015 to
430 31/10/2015.

431 The annual results of ED_y and the amount of irrigation and drained water are shown in
432 Fig. 8. It can be observed that all the case studies achieved ED_y values higher than 43%.
433 The strategy that achieved the highest ED_y value was C1₈₀, 78.7%, with 2660 l/m² of
434 annual irrigation water, see Fig. 8. However, this strategy also presented a significant
435 annual drainage value, 191 l/m², so 7.2 % of water was not used to reduce the heat flux
436 of the roof. The strategy C1₆₀ also achieved a high annual ED_y value, 76.6%, even with a
437 lower amount of annual irrigation water, 1995 l/m², and lower annual drainage, 159 l/m²,
438 than those of C1₈₀. A significant annual ED_y value was obtained with the strategy C1₄₀,
439 62.8%. The amount of annual irrigation water used for C1₄₀ was 1330 l/m², 50% and
440 33.3% less than the amount of annual water used for C1₈₀ and C1₆₀, respectively.
441 Furthermore, a low annual drainage value was found for C1₄₀, a 5% of irrigation water
442 was drained. The case C0, that had no irrigation schedule, also achieved a significant
443 annual ED value, 43.3%, due to the insulation effect of the substrate, see Fig. 8.

444 Therefore, it can be said that the installation of an eco-roof significantly improved the
445 thermal performance of the building compared to a traditional gravel ballasted roof,
446 achieving a high percentage of ED_y . In addition, adequate irrigation strategies allowed a
447 further increase of this ED, up to 78.7% for C1₈₀.

448

449 Fig. 8. Annual results of the reduction of energy demand, P_{eco}, irrigation and drainage.

450 The annual P_{eco} results are also shown in Fig. 8. This parameter was used to evaluate the

451 irrigation strategies that had the highest reduction of energy demand with respect to the

452 lowest quantity of irrigation water, expressed by Eq. (6). It can be observed that the

453 strategy with the highest P_{eco} value was C5₂₀, 153.9 [kWh/l year], mainly due to the low

454 quantity of irrigation water, 380 l/m², see Fig. 8. C5₂₀ also presented the lowest annual

455 drainage, only 1 l/m². Among the cases with the same irrigation schedule, the highest P_{eco}

456 values were always found for C5, the strategies with irrigation in alternate days. For the

457 remaining cases with the same irrigation schedule, the highest P_{eco} values were obtained

458 for C1, the cases with irrigation once a day at 9:00 am, as shown in Fig. 8, due to the high

459 reduction of energy demand achieved with the eco-roof with respect to the traditional

460 roof. The lowest P_{eco} values were found for C4, the cases with irrigation once a day at

461 1:00 pm.

462 Therefore, in the present work, an irrigation strategy on alternate days watering for 20

463 min in the morning, allowed an ED_y value up to 46.7 % with respect to the traditional

464 gravel ballasted roof, and with a low waste of irrigation water to be achieved.

465 4 CONCLUSIONS

466 In this work, an analysis of the thermal performance of an eco-roof under 20 different
467 irrigation strategies, compared to a traditional gravel ballasted roof, was carried out.
468 Hence, a building model with two different roofs, an eco-roof and a traditional gravel
469 ballasted roof, was calibrated with experimental data of heat flux. The study was
470 performed during the year 2015 for the climatic conditions of Córdoba (Spain). An
471 analysis based on evapotranspiration, ET, volumetric water content of the substrate,
472 VWC, heat flux, \dot{Q} , and energy demand, ED, was performed.

473 The weekly results showed that the ET values increased when the values of outdoor air
474 temperature, wind speed and solar radiation rose, and outdoor air relative humidity values
475 decreased. The VWC value of the substrate also had a significant impact on ET during
476 the summer, such that the higher the VWC, the higher the ET. The highest average ET
477 values for the summer were obtained for the strategies with irrigation once a day at 8:30
478 am for 60 min and 80 min. The results obtained for the winter showed that average ET
479 values did not have a significant variation when the VWC and irrigation strategy were
480 modified.

481 ET had a great impact on the reduction of \dot{Q} of the eco-roof, since the weekly \dot{Q} values
482 were reduced when weekly ET values increased. The lowest weekly \dot{Q} values were
483 achieved for the strategies with irrigation once a day at 8:30 am for 60 min and 80 min,
484 coinciding with the highest weekly ET. The greatest reduction of weekly \dot{Q} were always
485 achieved by watering every day during the morning.

486 The annual results showed that the installation of the eco-roof significantly improved the
487 thermal performance of the building compared to the traditional gravel ballasted roof,
488 achieving a high percentage of ED, 43.3% for the case without irrigation. Moreover, the
489 irrigation strategies further increased the ED values, up to 78.7% for the strategies with

490 irrigation once a day at 8:30 am for 80 min. However, for this irrigation strategy, a
491 percentage of water used for irrigation was drained, so this did not contribute to further
492 reduce \dot{Q} of the eco-roof. The strategy that had the highest energy savings with respect to
493 the highest usage of irrigation water was the irrigation strategy on alternate days watering
494 20 min, achieving an ED value up to 46.7 %, with low waste of irrigation water.
495 These results strengthen the performance analysis of eco-roofs with a proper irrigation
496 strategy, as well as their use as an interesting passive system for the rehabilitation of old
497 buildings.

498

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509

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